

1 Title:

2 Influence of the final ethanol concentration on the acetification and production rate in the
3 wine vinegar process.

4

5 Short title:

6 Influence of the final ethanol concentration on the acetification rate.

7

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21 **Abstract**

22 **BACKGROUND:** The acetification process still needs an overall study of the variables
23 influencing it in order to establish their optimum values. Based on industrial experience and
24 available literature, including a recently proposed model by the authors, amongst the variables
25 most strongly influencing the acetification process are the ethanol concentration at the time the

1 reactor is unloaded, the unloaded volume and the loading rate. In the scope of ensuring
2 economically efficient industrial production of vinegar, as well as checking the predictions by
3 the aforementioned model, the influence of the final ethanol concentration at unloading time
4 on the mean acetification rate and on productivity has been studied in this work.

5 **RESULTS:** An increase in the final ethanol concentration from 0.5 to 3.5 % (v/v) increases
6 the mean overall acetification rate and acetic acid production by 38 and 26 %, respectively.

7 The increase is mainly established during the loading phase.

8 **CONCLUSIONS:** The final ethanol concentration is a key variable for the process
9 optimization. If a high rate is desired then a product containing much unused substrate will be
10 obtained, which may be industrially unacceptable. These results suggest the necessity to
11 investigate other possibilities when high values for yield and productivities must to be
12 achieved.

13

14 *Keywords:* Vinegar, wine vinegar, *acetobacter*, acetic acid, fed-batch culture, optimization.

15

16 **NOTATION**

17 $(-r_E)$ Ethanol uptake rate, mL ethanol \cdot (100 mL medium \cdot h)⁻¹ \equiv % (v/v) \cdot h⁻¹

18 r_A Acetification rate, g acetic acid \cdot (100 mL medium \cdot h)⁻¹ \equiv % (w/v) \cdot h⁻¹

19 P_A Acetic acid production, g acetic acid \cdot h⁻¹

20 $(-r_E)_{LP1}$ Mean ethanol uptake rate during loading phase 1, % (v/v) \cdot h⁻¹

21 $(-r_E)_{LP2}$ Mean ethanol uptake rate during loading phase 2, % (v/v) \cdot h⁻¹

22 $(-r_E)_{PP}$ Mean ethanol uptake rate during production phase, % (v/v) \cdot h⁻¹

23 $(-r_E)_{Global}$ Mean overall ethanol uptake rate, % (v/v) \cdot h⁻¹

24

1 INTRODUCTION

2 Industrially, wine vinegar is obtained mainly by using a semi-continuous process
3 involving submerged acetic acid bacteria¹⁻⁴. Specifically, once the alcohol content falls below
4 a preset level, a portion of the culture medium is unloaded, that remaining in the reactor acting
5 as inoculum for the next load. This allows the production of high-acidity vinegar, facilitates
6 the use of part of the biomass formed in each load to rapidly ferment the next and alters the
7 conditions of the medium in such a way that it can be efficiently used by the most suitable
8 organisms for the intended purpose⁵⁻¹⁰.

9 This operational procedure affords easier control of some variables including the
10 ethanol concentration at unloading time, unloaded volume and loading rate. Such variables
11 influence the concentration and activity of acetic acid bacteria as they act simultaneously on
12 the acidity, ethanol concentration, oxygen supply and even temperature of the medium.

13 Although a wealth of knowledge currently exists on the vinegar production process,
14 there remains the need to optimize the previous variables, which may have a significant effect
15 on the fermentation rate^{4, 11-19}.

16 Recently, a review with previous attempts for modeling the process as well as a new
17 model proposal has been published^{4, 17, 18}. According to this model, the operational conditions
18 depend of the specific type of product to be obtained. If a high rate is desired, the final ethanol
19 content should not be very low, otherwise the bacterial cells may be severely affected by the
20 scarcity of substrate and the high acidity of the medium, which can seriously hinder their reuse
21 on the next load¹⁸.

22 This paper reports the results of a study of the influence of the ethanol concentration at
23 unloading time on the productivity and overall rate of the acetification process.

24

1 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2 Raw material

3 The raw material used was white wine from the Montilla-Moriles region (Córdoba,
4 Spain) with an ethanol content of 12.0 % (v/v) \pm 0.3 and an initial acidity of 0.2 % (w/v).

6 Microorganisms

7 The inoculum used consisted of a mixed bacterial culture of the genera *Acetobacter*
8 and *Gluconobacter* where *Acetobacter aceti* and *Acetobacter pasteurianus* were the
9 predominant species²⁰. The inoculum was obtained from a fully operational industrial
10 fermentation tank of the firm Grupo SOS, in its Alcolea factory (Córdoba, Spain).

12 Analytical methods

13 Acidity was determined by acid-base titration and ethanol quantified on-line by means of an
14 Alkosens[®] probe (Heinrich Frings (<http://www.frings.com>))

16 Fermentation conditions

17 Tests were conducted in a Frings 8 L fermentation tank, operated in a semi-continuous mode
18 consisting of the following steps:

19 (1) Depletion of ethanol in the medium (production phase, PP) to a concentration
20 of 0.5, 1.5, 2.5 or 3.5 % (v/v) at a constant temperature of 31 °C and an also
21 constant air flow-rate of 7.5 L air h⁻¹ · L⁻¹ medium. Once the desired ethanol
22 concentration was reached, 50 % of the tank contents were unloaded.

23 (2) Regarding the loading phase, several strategies are possible. Nevertheless, the
24 aforementioned model by the authors¹⁸, suggest that the charging step must be
25 carried out in such a way as to keep the ethanol concentration within the

1 approximate range 5-6 % (v/v). Ethanol levels around and above 6 % (v/v) reduce
2 the proportions of viable cells as well as influence negatively the bacterial activity.
3 So, the tank was slowly loaded (feed rate of $1.2 \text{ L}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$) to an ethanol concentration
4 never exceeding 5 % (v/v). This was done in two steps: loading phase 1 (LP1) and
5 loading phase 2 (LP2). In the first, the tank was loaded in a continuous manner to
6 an ethanol concentration of 5 % (v/v); in the second, more wine was added in a
7 semi-continuous manner until the desired final working volume (8 L) was
8 completed.

9 The bioreactor was fully equipped to operate in an automated mode. Loading,
10 unloading, control and monitoring operations were performed unattended via a previously
11 programmed computer.

12 Because the primary purpose of this work was to compare the influence of the target
13 operating conditions on the overall rate of the process, the rate had to be previously
14 determined. Provided the total strength remained roughly constant and identical with that of
15 the starting wine throughout the cycle, the ethanol and acetic entrainment losses are negligible,
16 so the mean fermentation rate can be estimated both from the variation of the ethanol
17 concentration during the cycle²¹ and from the final acidity.

18 The fermentation rate determination from the ethanol concentration, $(-r_E)$, allows one
19 to establish the variation of the acetification rate throughout the cycle, so it is possible to
20 assess the influence of the operational variables on the different steps of the process. Details of
21 how estimating the mean acetification rate via on-line monitored changes in ethanol during a
22 semi-continuous vinegar production cycle can be found elsewhere²¹.

23 At the same time, the mean acetification rate, r_A , can be easily calculated from the final
24 acidity in the medium at unloading time, the unloaded volume, the cycle duration and the
25 weighted mean of the fermentation broth volume:

1

$$r_A = \frac{\text{final acetic acid concentration (\% (w/v))} \cdot \text{unloaded volume (L medium)}}{\text{cycle time (h)} \cdot \text{mean overall volume (L)}} \quad (1)$$

2
3

4 By way of example, eq. (2) shows the calculation of r_A for a final ethanol concentration
5 of 0.5 % (v/v).

6

$$r_A = \frac{11.0 \% (w/v) \cdot 4 \text{ L medium}}{31.9 \text{ h} \cdot 7.68 \text{ L}} = 0.18 \frac{\% (w/v)}{\text{h}} \quad (2)$$

7
8

9 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

10 As stated above, wine vinegar is usually obtained by using a semi-continuous
11 fermentation process involving periodic unloading of the fermentation medium. The ethanol
12 concentration present at the time the reactor is unloaded is one of the variables most strongly
13 influencing the overall fermentation rate. In fact, the more markedly ethanol is depleted, the
14 largest is the amount of acid formed –with which bacteria may eventually react. In this work,
15 the influence of ethanol concentrations of 0.5, 1.5, 2.5 and 3.5 % (v/v) were studied. For
16 instant, Figure 1 shows the variation of the ethanol content, acidity and volume of the medium
17 during the acetification cycle at the ethanol concentration of 1.5 % (v/v). The figure, which
18 shows the results of 8 tests, clearly exposes the steps involved in the fermentation cycle
19 (particularly the ethanol and volume data). Table 1 list the duration of loading and production
20 phases, the time and final acidity values, as well as the average volume for all the experiments;
21 data are accompanied by their respective standard deviations. Table 2 lists the ethanol uptake
22 rate ($-r_E$) for each phase and global values, the mean acetification rate r_A values, as well as the
23 production of acetic acid, P_A , in g acetic acid \cdot h⁻¹.

1 Figure 2 shows the acetification rate and acetic acid production percent differences
2 from the lowest levels (viz. those leading to a final ethanol concentration of 0.5 % (v/v)) as
3 well as the mean overall ethanol and acetic acid concentrations for each case. As can be seen,
4 the acetification rate and the acetic acid production increased with increasing ethanol
5 concentration at unloading time by about 38 and 26 %, respectively.

6 Based on the sensitivity of acetic acid bacteria to both the substrate and product, and on
7 changes in the culture medium, one can expect them to perform disparately under different
8 experimental conditions^{4, 22-24}. In fact, our tests exposed differences in mean overall acidity
9 and ethanol concentration (Fig. 2), and also in the highest acidity level reached (Table 1). A
10 high acidity is invariably accompanied by a low ethanol concentration. Both can adversely
11 affect the overall rate of the process, ethanol because it is the limiting substrate and acetic acid
12 because of its inhibitory effect increases with increasing concentration⁴. In this case, the
13 known negative influence that high ethanol concentrations can have on cell viability –
14 demonstrated by authors elsewhere⁴, it is not a problem because of the followed loading
15 strategy by which the ethanol concentration was never higher than 5 % (v/v). Nevertheless, the
16 acetic acid concentration could be the key factor for explaining the differences observed in this
17 work. Indeed, a decrease in bacterial viability is normally observed as the mean acetic acid
18 concentration increases and, specially, when maxima (final) acidities reach 11 % (w/v)⁴.

19 The process can also be affected by changes occurring between unloading and the end
20 of the loading process; such changes become more marked as the substrate is depleted as well
21 as the loading step is shortened. For instant, Figure 3 shows regression for the experimental
22 variation of ethanol content and volume of the medium during the cycle at each studied final
23 ethanol concentration. From the first, it can be seen that, during the loading phase, bacteria are
24 subjected to important differences in the ethanol concentration (and therefore in acidity) which
25 may have a negative influence in the process. On the other side, from the second, it can be

1 seen that, from a kinetic point of view, main differences are found in the loading phase 2.
2 During this step, where the ethanol concentration is kept constant, the fermentation rate can be
3 estimated from the temporal variation of the volume²¹.

4 Table 2 lists the ethanol uptake rates for each phase throughout the cycle.

5 Provide ethanol uptake rates during loading phase 1 (Table 2) have not statistically
6 significant differences (one way ANOVA test), must be in loading phase 2 and production
7 phase where the increase of acetification rate is established. As can be calculated from data
8 listed on Table 2, the uptake ethanol rate for loading phase 2 and production phase increased
9 with final ethanol concentration by about 82 and 13 %, respectively. Nevertheless the overall
10 rate of ethanol uptake increased just by about 40 % since a weighted average as a function of
11 the proportion of time taken by each phase has to be considered. In any case, it is clear that
12 main differences are found in loading phase 2.

13 Based on the previous results, which contribute to validate the previously proposed
14 model by the authors¹⁸, obtaining a high rate for the process entails ensuring a high ethanol
15 concentration at unloading time; this, however, considerably reduces the acetification yield
16 through the presence of a substantial amount of ethanol in the unloaded liquid. This
17 shortcoming can be circumvented, by using two serially arranged reactors. The two reactors
18 can be optimized in such a way as to ensure that the first is unloaded at a high concentration of
19 ethanol and the second depletes it before it receives a new load from the first; this study is at
20 present going on.

21

22 **5. Conclusions**

23 The semi-continuous wine acetification process usually employed by the vinegar
24 production industry can be improved as regards overall rate by optimizing some easily
25 adjusted process variables including the ethanol concentration at unloading time, unloaded

1 volume and loading charge. In this work, the influence of the ethanol concentration on the
2 production and mean acetification rate was studied. Based on the results, the acetification rate
3 and the production of acetic acid increase substantially with increase in the ethanol
4 concentration. Also it is concluded that the increase of the acetification rate is established
5 mainly during the loading phase. However, a product containing much unused substrate is
6 industrially unacceptable. For this reason, two serially arranged reactors, usually available in
7 industry, must be optimized in such a way that the first one must ensure a high acetification
8 rate, but also a final ethanol concentration that can be easily depleted in the second reactor
9 before it receives a new load from the first. This procedure should give mean overall
10 acetification rates higher than those typically obtained when the substrate is depleted much
11 more in the first reactor.

12

13 **Acknowledgements**

14 The authors wish to acknowledge funding of this research (AGL2002-01712,
15 PET2006-0827) by Spain's Ministry of Science and Technology (MCyT) and Ministry of
16 Science and Education. Also, they wish to thank the firm Grupo SOS (Spain) for valuable help
17 and advice.

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1

2 Table 1

Final ethanol concentration, % (v/v)	0.5	1.5	2.5	3.5
Number of cycles	6	8	10	29
Duration of loading phase 1, h	2.5 ± 0.1	2.1 ± 0.1	1.4 ± 0.1	0.9 ± 0.1
Duration of loading phase 2, h	6.8 ± 0.4	8.3 ± 0.7	8.9 ± 0.6	11.0 ± 0.8
Duration of production phase, h	22.6 ± 0.9	16.9 ± 0.8	12.0 ± 0.9	6.8 ± 1.2
Cycle duration, h	31.9 ± 0.8	27.3 ± 0.4	22.3 ± 0.5	18.7 ± 0.9
Final acidity (as acetic acid), % (w/v)	11.0 ± 0.2	10.1 ± 0.2	9.2 ± 0.15	8.1 ± 0.1
Mean total volume, L	7.68 ± 0.06	7.54 ± 0.03	7.37 ± 0.02	7.00 ± 0.02

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2 Table 2

Final ethanol concentration, % (v/v)	0.5	1.5	2.5	3.5
$(-rE)_{LP1}, \% (v/v) \cdot h^{-1}$	0.13 ± 0.10	0.23 ± 0.24	0.20 ± 0.17	0.29 ± 0.29
$(-rE)_{LP2}, \% (v/v) \cdot h^{-1}$	0.15 ± 0.01	0.19 ± 0.01	0.25 ± 0.01	0.28 ± 0.01
$(-rE)_{PP}, \% (v/v) \cdot h^{-1}$	0.20 ± 0.01	0.21 ± 0.01	0.22 ± 0.01	0.23 ± 0.01
$(-rE)_{Global}, \% (v/v) \cdot h^{-1}$	0.19 ± 0.01	0.20 ± 0.02	0.23 ± 0.02	0.26 ± 0.03
$r_A, \% (w/v) \cdot h^{-1}$	0.18 ± 0.01	0.20 ± 0.01	0.22 ± 0.01	0.25 ± 0.01
$P_A, g \text{ acetic acid} \cdot h^{-1}$	13.8 ± 0.4	14.8 ± 0.4	16.5 ± 0.5	17.4 ± 0.9

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4

1 All figures were created by SigmaPlot for Windows Version 11.0

2 Figure 1

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1 Figure 2

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1 Figure 3

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4

1 Legends

2

3 Table 1

4 Experimental phase and cycle duration, final acidity and mean overall volume obtained under

5 different experimental conditions plus their standard deviations.

6

7 Table 2

8 Phase and global ethanol uptake rate, mean acetification rate and acetic acid production,

9 accompanied by their standard deviations.

10

11 Figure 1

12 Variation of the ethanol concentration, volume and acidity of the medium during the

13 fermentation cycle. Final ethanol concentration at unloading time: 1.5 % (v/v). (LP1: loading

14 phase 1; LP2: loading phase 2; PP: production phase).

15

16 Figure 2

17 Acetification rate and acetic acid production percent differences from the lowest levels as well

18 as the mean overall ethanol and acetic acid concentrations. Bars represent standard deviations.

19

20 Figure 3

21 Regression for the experimental variation of ethanol content and volume of the medium during

22 the cycle at each studied final ethanol concentration.

23